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IMPORTANCE OF PROCESS MINING FOR BIG DATA REQUIREMENTS ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

Requirements engineering (RE), as a part of the project development life cycle, has increasingly been recognized as the key to ensure on-time, on-budget, and goal-based delivery of software projects. RE of big data projects is even more crucial because of the rapid growth of big data applications over the past few years. Data processing, being a part of big data RE, is an essential job in driving big data RE process successfully. Business can be overwhelmed by data and underwhelmed by the information so, data processing is very critical in big data projects. Employing traditional data processing techniques lacks the invention of useful information because of the main characteristics of big data, including high volume, velocity, and variety. Data processing can be benefited by process mining, and in turn, helps to increase the productivity of the big data projects. In this paper, the capability of process mining in big data RE to discover valuable insights and business values from event logs and processes of the systems has been highlighted. Also, the proposed big data requirements engineering framework, named REBD, helps software requirements engineers to eradicate many challenges of big data RE.

KEYWORDS

Big data, requirements engineering, requirements elicitation, data processing, knowledge discovery, process mining

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XML ENCRYPTION AND SIGNATURE FOR SECURING WEB SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

In this research, we have focused on the most challenging issue that Web Services face, i.e. how to secure their information. Web Services security could be guaranteed by employing security standards, which is the main focus of this search. Every suggested model related to security design should put in the account the securities' objectives; integrity, confidentiality, non- repudiation, authentication, and authorization. The proposed model describes SOAP messages and the way to secure their contents. Due to the reason that SOAP message is the core of the exchanging information in Web Services, this research has developed a security model needed to ensure e-business security. The essence of our model depends on XML encryption and XML signature to encrypt and sign SOAP message. The proposed model looks forward to achieve a high speed of transaction and a strong level of security without jeopardizing the performance of transmission information.

KEYWORDS

Web Services, SOAP, SAML, XKMS, IDEA, RSA.

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VARIATIONS IN OUTCOME FOR THE SAME MAP REDUCE TRANSITIVE CLOSURE ALGORITHM IMPLEMENTED ON DIFFERENT HADOOP PLATFORMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the outcome of an attempt to implement the same transitive closure (TC) algorithm for Apache MapReduce running on different Apache Hadoop distributions. Apache MapReduce is a software framework used with Apache Hadoop, which has become the de facto standard platform for processing and storing large amounts of data in a distributed computing environment. The research presented here focuses on the variations observed among the results of an efficient iterative transitive closure algorithm when run against different distributed environments. The results from these comparisons were validated against the benchmark results from OYSTER, an open source Entity Resolution system. The experiment results highlighted the inconsistencies that can occur when using the same codebase with different implementations of Map Reduce.

KEYWORDS

Entity Resolution; Hadoop; MapReduce; Transitive Closure; HDFS; Cloudera; Talend

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CONSTRAINT-BASED AND FUZZY LOGIC STUDENT MODELING FOR ARABIC GRAMMAR

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ABSTRACT

Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) are computer-based tutoring systems that deal with linguistic skills. Adding intelligence in such systems is mainly based on using Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools to diagnose student errors, especially in language grammar. However, most such systems do not consider the modeling of student competence in linguistic skills, especially for the Arabic language. In this paper, we will deal with basic grammar concepts of the Arabic language taught for the fourth grade of the elementary school in Egypt. This is through Arabic Grammar Trainer (AGTrainer) which is an Intelligent CALL. The implemented system (AGTrainer) trains the students through different questions that deal with the different concepts and have different difficulty levels. Constraint-based student modeling (CBSM) technique is used as a short-term student model. CBSM is used to define in small grain level the different grammar skills through the defined skill structures. The main contribution of this paper is the hierarchal representation of the system's basic grammar skills as domain knowledge. That representation is used as a mechanism for efficiently checking constraints to model the student knowledge and diagnose the student errors and identify their cause. In addition, satisfying constraints and the number of trails the student takes for answering each question and fuzzy logic decision system are used to determine the student learning level for each lesson as a long-term model. The results of the evaluation showed the system's effectiveness in learning in addition to the satisfaction of students and teachers with its features and abilities.

KEYWORDS

Language Tutoring Systems, Student Model, Constraint-Based Modeling, Fuzzy logic

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THE SMART PARKING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

With growing, Car parking increases with the number of car users. With the increased use of smartphones and their applications, users prefer mobile phone-based solutions. This paper proposes the Smart Parking Management System (SPMS) that depends on Arduino parts, Android applications, and based on IoT. This gave the client the ability to check available parking spaces and reserve a parking spot. IR sensors are utilized to know if a car park space is allowed. Its area data are transmitted using the WI-FI module to the server and are recovered by the mobile application which offers many options attractively and with no cost to users and lets the user check reservation details. With IoT technology, the smart parking system can be connected wirelessly to easily track available locations.

KEYWORDS

Internet of Things, Cloud Computing, Smart Parking, Smart City, Mobile Application.

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PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF LTE NETWORK USING MAXIMUM FLOW ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a new traffic flow model of the Long Term Evaluation (LTE) network for the Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access Network (E-UTRAN). Here only one Evolve Node B (eNB) nearest to the Mobility Management Entity (MME) and Serving Gateway (S-GW) will use the S1 link to bridge the E-UTRAN and Evolved Packet Core (EPC). All the eNBs of a tracking area will be connected to each other by the X2 link. Determination of capacity of a links of such a network is a challenging job since each node offers its own traffic and at the same time conveys traffic of other nodes. In this paper, we apply maximum flow algorithm including superposition theorem to solve the traffic flow of radio network. Using the total flow per subcarrier, a new traffic model is also developed in the paper. The relation among the traffic parameters: 'blocking probability', 'offered traffic', 'instantaneous capacity', 'average holding time', and 'number of users' are shown graphically under both QPSK and 16-QAM. The concept of the network will be helpful to improve the SINR of the received signal of eNBs located long distance relative to MME/S-GW.

KEYWORDS

Aggregate offered traffic, blocking probability, traffic channel, weighted graph and RB.

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A NOVEL STUDY OF LICHEN PLANOPILARIS AMONG DIFFERENT IRANIAN ETHNICITIES BASED ON COMPUTER-AIDED PROGRAMS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Demographic studies of a disease can reveal the characteristics of that disease among a specific population and will help the physicians to achieve a more accurate perception about it. The demographic of Lichen PlanoPilaris (LPP) among the Iranian population is unknown. The aim of this study is to describe the clinical, demographic, and histopathologic findings of lichen planopilaris in the Iranian population.

Materials and Methods: In this cross-sectional study, all the patients with Lichen planopilaris were referred to the dermatology clinic of Imam Khomeini hospital from 2013 to 2015. Lichen planopilaris can be diagnosed by collecting histological evidence, dermatological examination, and clinical diagnosis. Their demographic characteristics, drug histories, onset of disease, and family histories were obtained by written questionnaire. Additionally, this study employed SPSS v.20 as the statistical analysis software.

Results: One hundred patients were enrolled in this study. With an average age of 47.11 years, 78% of the patients were female, and 50 of these were housewives. The patients included were often from Tehran with Fars ethnicity. Among these patients, 7 had alopecia areata skin disease, and 10 of them suffered from thyroid disease. Most of the histopathology samples collected from these biopsies revealed degeneration of the basal layer of the follicular structure, perifollicular fibrosis, inflammatory cells, and atrophy of the pilosebaceous structures.

Conclusion: Both the age spectrum and the disease distribution of LPP among the Iranian population were very diverse when compared to previous studies. Moreover, this study helps the physicians to have a brighter vision about the main reason and cause of LPP spread among diverse Iranian Ethnicities.

KEYWORDS

Clinical Features, Epidemiologic, Demographics, Histology, Lichen PlanoPilaris (LPP), Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

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RAILWAY SAFETY PROTECTION WITH ANDROID MOBILE APPLICATION FOR 5G NEW RADIO NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

In every night of non-traffic hours, different jobs are conducting maintenance works in "Railway" trackside area. This project will explain a specific section of track under the sole control an Engineer's Person-in-Charge as procedures. And how to provide protection methods by which a person or persons on or near a track are safeguarded from potential train movements or a train is safeguarded from other train movements or obstructions, or persons or equipment are safeguarded from traction power. Consolidated past several investigation reports and according to related is rules, workflow or procedures etc. to summarize. There are protection tools left on trackside area incident caused by the workers are forgetting and poor management. Proposed are different project themes in the light of their expertise, experience and observation in their daily works. The proposed themes are compared, assessed and prioritized under the criteria - "Manageable", "Measurable", "Result of Benefit", "Standardization" and "Priority" in the Decision Matrix. Establish some solve problem methods for comparing to find out which that lower-cost plan accordingly. I came up with a conclusion and the ideas as develop a mobile application and create a unique QR code label with equipment naming to facilitate each worker management of protection tools. This is also fulfilled in popular terms of Creativity and Innovations. Used the MIT App Inventor (Massachusetts Institute of technology) an intuitive and visual programming preform for mobile application are development. Stage 1: program for individual mobile user application. Stage 2: build-up Network centralized storage with supervising console operation. Stage 3: testing system under with 5G network compatibility, bandwidth and network speed is applicable people will be able to use more of the network dedicated to each mobile phone. Finally, successful to apply trial works a fruitful outcome after implementation of the project solution. There was no missing of protection tools on trackside area within the trial period. With the safety-first culture boosted by us, I believe we can achieve a common goal: Everyone Going Home Safe and Well Every day.

KEYWORDS

Railway Trackside Safety, QR code, Network Centralized Storage, 5G Mobile Network,

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